
ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL MODEL PARAMETER ESTIMATION USING GENETIC ALGORITHMS AND DEEP DETERMINISTIC POLICY GRADIENTS

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The FitzHugh-Nagumo is a model for examining the dynamics of excitable systems, encompassing cardiac and neuronal electrophysiology [1]. Accurately representing excitable systems is imperative for a comprehensive understanding of their behavior and potential applications in medical research and computational biology. The FitzHugh-Nagumo is an attractive candidate for modeling excitable dynamics, since it balances between simplicity and realism. Nonetheless, the manual tuning of parameters to align with experimental data is laborious and often yields suboptimal outcomes. However, the precise determination of model parameters remains a formidable challenge due to the system's sensitivity to parameter variations.

In this study, we present the application of genetic algorithms (GA) and deep deterministic policy gradients (DDPG) to optimize FitzHugh-Nagumo model parameters [2, 3]. Genetic algorithms, drawing inspiration from natural selection, present an efficient means to automate parameter optimization [2]. Parameters for membrane potential, recovery variable, and calcium concentration were optimized based on desired action potential or based on desired calcium concentration. The genetic algorithm systematically explored the parameter space, selecting and recombining parameter sets to maximize the model's fidelity to predefined observations [2]. The optimization process adhered to the principles of natural selection, mutation, and crossover, facilitating the exploration of diverse parameter combinations. At the end of genetic algorithm optimization, deep deterministic policy gradients were applied to further refine the solution and enhance accuracy [2, 3].

Our results attest to the efficacy of the combined genetic algorithm and deep deterministic policy gradients approach in fine-tuning FitzHugh-Nagumo model parameters, resulting in a notable alignment with the desired action potential. The application of genetic algorithms and deep deterministic policy gradients for FitzHugh-Nagumo model parameter optimization represents a promising trajectory for advancing the applicability of this model. Mathematically, the optimization process amplifies the model's proficiency in capturing the intricate dynamics of excitable systems. Biomechanically, the refined parameters yield a more physiologically relevant representation, unlocking novel avenues for investigating complex phenomena in cardiac and neuronal electrophysiology [4, 5]. This study underscores the significance of optimization techniques in bridging the gap between mathematical modeling and biological reality, thereby paving the way for an improved understanding and enhanced predictive capabilities in

excitable system research.

Key words: FitzHugh-Nagumo, electrophysiology, genetic algorithms, deep deterministic policy gradients

Acknowledgement: The research was supported by the STRATIFYHF project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101080905. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or granting authority - European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This research is also part of the project of multilateral collaboration in the Danube region, No. 337-00-140/2023-05/05 titled "Synergy of multiscale Modelling and machine Learning: Strategy for biomedical sciences and battle against cancer". This research was also supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952603 (<http://sgabu.eu/>), and it was also funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, contract number [451-03-68/2023-14/200107 (Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac) and 451-03-68/2023-14/200378 (Institute of Information Technologies, University of Kragujevac)]. The authors acknowledge support from the City of Kragujevac, Serbia.

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